

THE IMAGE OF A FEMALE HERO IN UZBEK PROSE

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Annotation. The problem of image creation in literature and the research of knowledge and skills obtained by comparing images is one of the urgent issues of today's modern literature. By comparing the images in each work, in the process of comparative analysis, new information is obtained about the compared object. This thesis examines important theoretical approaches in the comparative analysis of Uzbek prose.

Key words: prose, modern prose, image, comparative analysis, realistic spirit, literature

Абстракт. Проблема создания образа в литературе и исследования знаний и умений, полученных путем сравнения образов, является одной из актуальных проблем сегодняшней современной литературы. Путем сравнения изображений в каждом произведении в процессе сравнительного анализа получают новую информацию о сравниваемом объекте. В данной диссертации рассматриваются важные теоретические подходы в сравнительном анализе узбекской прозы.

Ключевые слова: проза, современная проза, образ, сравнительный анализ, реалистический дух, литература.

Although classical Uzbek and English literature, as well as the literature of many other countries, presented different genres to the world of literature, we can see that their development, national history and religion are closely related. English and Uzbek prose has a rich history and is known to the world for its famous works and writers. Among them, we can cite Balkhi, Rabguzi, Navoi,

Saidadin Muhammad and many other Turkish prose writers who created in the 10th-12th centuries.

Despite the fact that the prose of the two nations of ancient times began to open its buds between the V-IX centuries, it changed its forms and reached the form of prose for several centuries before that.

Despite the works created in the 10th-12th centuries, Rabguzi's "Kissasi Rabguzi" written at the beginning of the 14th century, Navoi's "Mahbub ul Qulub" written at the beginning of the 14th century, especially the creation of "Boburnoma" are the main national prose works in Uzbek literature. The edges became radiant. In the same way, it should be noted that prose began to develop in the 14th century under the influence of religious beliefs in English literature.

English and Uzbek literature has gone through a long and difficult path of development. It is known that our literature, which is recorded as Uzbek classical literature, is actually a literary monument created by the peoples who lived in Central Asia since ancient times. Also, literature in the Turkish language, which was created in the X-XII centuries, is not only related to the Uzbek people, but also the common spiritual wealth of the Turkic peoples living in Central Asia and Eastern Turkestan.

Uzbek classical literature has created beautiful female heroines, among them, we can find Zulaiho from Rabguzi's "The Tale of Rabguzi", the old woman in a coat, Nigorkhanim from Baburnoma and others.

In the Uzbek literature of that time, there were a few works written in prose style, and female heroines were rarely embodied in them. It can be seen that women were not considered as the basis of society in that period according to religious views. The female characters embodied in the few works are presented only as information about some examples of the owners of beauty and intelligence and the women of the horns.

In the process of studying and analyzing the 10th-18th centuries, we can observe that in the prose of that period, there are few textual images, and in the

prose, only realistic heroic images are relied on. Between those periods, we can find a lot of images of textile women in works written in verse, from this it can be seen that between the X-XVIII centuries prose was not so developed, we can see that written prose works were created only as historical works based on real events. possible The female characters of the ancient English and Uzbek literature, unlike the female characters of the modern literature, have a holistic character and real events, which allows to restore the female characteristics of that time.

As mentioned above, in the prose works of the ancient period, realistic characters are depicted, and in them many characteristics of the female characters that are considered traditional nowadays: a spouse with positive characteristics such as charm, gentleness, care, hard work and obedience. , there are images of mother, daughter and housewife. The images of women who lived in different conditions in different images are connected by one aspect, and that is the love for the motherland. Because in those times, the fate of humanity was closely connected with the fate of the motherland.

In the following centuries, under the influence of the development of literature and social-political, social-historical changes, the image of a woman in the works was continuously improved. The characters of the heroes became more and more complex and full of dialectical spirit, and the authors began to pay more attention to the inner world and psychology of the heroes. It is known that the image of a woman has been depicted in Uzbek literature since ancient times. An example of this is the Avesta book, which is said to have been found in the country of Khorezm, written in Turkish language, and written in prose style, and we can find many images of women in it. The heroes covered in this book have a mythological miraculous character, the female goddesses Anahita and Anahid are depicted as symbols of the power of nature, and Toza is the goddess of knowledge. In addition, there are several historical female characters presented in the book, in particular, Zarathustra's mother (Dog'du); Shehrnaz and Ernewoz, daughters of the

Iranian king Jemshid; Female characters were created, such as Djakhika, the daughter of Akhremanni.

We can often find that a perfect, beautiful woman who always takes care of her family and has spiritual beauty is described not only in ancient Uzbek literature, but also in ancient English literature.

In the Uzbek mutoz prose, which was created a century later, we should also highlight the autobiographical prose work. Babur created a prose work based on his life, customs of that time, the geographical location of the state, and some information about the rulers in "Boburnoma", which was written in the years 1518-1530 of the 16th century. In Uzbek literature, which can be called an important monument in world literature and source studies, the first prose memoir and historical-scientific work "Boburnoma" was written in the old Uzbek language and is rich in pure artistic images, vivid images, and traditional lyrical digressions. Analyzing the women described by Babur in "Boburnoma", we can get information about the place of women in society and their relationships in that period. About sixty women's characters are described in Baburnoma, and each character is described differently based on the situation and character of the hero of the work.

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